

Electrophoretic Behaviour of some Transition Metal Ions on Tin(IV) Diethanolamine Impregnated Papers. Quantitative Separations of Silver(I) and Gold(III) from other Metal Ions

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Manuscript received 17 November 1989, revised 17 August 1990, accepted 21 September 1992

The analytical importance of chelating ion-exchangers in the field of separation and preconcentration of metal ions has received attention owing to their high selectivity¹. Papers impregnated with inorganic ion-exchangers have been extensively used for chromatographic separation of metal ions. Electrophoresis of metal ions on papers impregnated with inorganic ion-exchangers plays an important role in separation science². Rawat and Iqbal³ studied the selective uptake of metal ions on tin(IV) diethanolamine. Literature survey shows that no inorganic chelating ion-exchanger has been reported as an impregnating material in electrophoresis for the separation of metal ions. In this paper, electrophoretic behaviour of fifteen transition metal ions on tin(IV) diethanolamine (TDE) impregnated papers is investigated. Six background electrolytes were used at fixed voltage and time intervals. On the basis of migration of metal ions under the combined influence of electric field and sorption behaviour of TDE, some analytically important binary and ternary separations have been achieved on these impregnated papers.

Results and Discussion

Electrophoretic migration distances determined for 15 transition metal ions in six background electrolyte solutions on tin(IV) diethanolamine impregnated papers are presented in Table 1. The rate

of migration of charged metal species on TDE chelating ion-exchanger impregnated papers under a potential gradient depends, in principle, upon the sorption tendency of TDE and also on the nature and concentration of electrolytes. Sorption of metal ions on impregnated papers is likely due to the presence of nitrogen atoms in the amine group which offers site for chelation with the metal ions. Since, stability of metal-ligand (amine) complex depends upon pH of the background electrolyte, the migration rates are different in differed pH systems (Table 1). The mobility of cations decreases with the increased pH except in case of Fe^{III}, Au^{III} and Ag^I for which migration is zero. Electrophoretic migration has also been investigated in presence of EDTA and thiourea (TU) as complexing ligands. The mobility of metal ions is found to increase in EDTA-HCl system, except in case of Au^{III}, Ag^I and Ru^{III}. This may be due to the reason that these metal ions do not form complex with EDTA. Similarly, in case of TU-HCl system increased migration for Pt^{IV} and Ru^{III} has been observed. This can be explained on the basis of metal-TU complex formation.

On the basis of differences in migration distances and the direction of movement of cations several analytically important binary and ternary separations have been possible (Table 2). The analytical potentiality of tin(IV) diethanolamine impregnated papers is demonstrated by achieving quantitative

TABLE 1—MOVEMENT (cm) OF METAL IONS IN VARIOUS ELECTROLYTES ON TIN(IV) DIETHANOLAMINE IMPREGNATED PAPERS

Metal ion	Time=3 h, Voltage applied=200 V					
	0.2M KCl+ 0.2M HCl pH 1	0.2M KCl+ 0.2M HCl pH 2	0.2M CH ₃ COOH+ 0.2M CH ₃ COONa pH 4	0.1M CH ₃ COOH+ 0.1M CH ₃ COONa pH 6	0.01M EDTA in 0.1M HCl	0.1M TU in 0.01M HCl
Cu ^{II}	-3.4	-3.0	-2.6	-1.0	-3.8	-1.7
Co ^{II}	-2.0	-1.6	-1.3	-1.0	-2.7	-0.5
Fe ^{III}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-1.7	0.0
Ni ^{II}	-2.0	-1.8	-1.5	-1.0	-0.5	-0.7
Zn ^{II}	-0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.8	0.0
Au ^{III}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Cd ^{II}	-1.0	-0.8	-0.5	0.0	-1.2	0.0
Hg ^{II}	3.9	3.7	3.6	2.3	4.8	0.0
Pt ^{IV}	6.5	6.3	6.1	2.0	14.0	11.6
Ru ^{III}	6.0	5.2	0.7	0.6	2.3	17.4
Pd ^{II}	-11.5	-10.4	-10.0	-2.2	-18.0	0.0
Cr ^{VI}	-3.6	-3.3	-3.2	-3.0	-3.9	-4.0
Mn ^{II}	-0.8	-0.6	-0.5	-0.3	-2.8	-1.0
Mo ^{VI}	-3.0	-2.8	-2.8	-2.7	-3.2	-3.5
Ag ^I	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

NOTES

separations of gold(I) and silver(I) in presence of other metal ions. On the basis of the observed qualitative separations, these quantitative separations were carried out in pH 1 system in only 3 h under a potential of 200 V. Ag^{I} (2–10 μg) and Ag^{III} (2–10 μg) could be separated quantitatively from Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Hg^{II} , Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} (5 μg each) in the synthetic mixture.

acid in demineralised water. Standard spot-test reagents were used for detection.

Six aqueous background electrolyte solutions were used for electrophoretic study: (i) 0.2 M KCl+0.2 M HCl (pH 1), (ii) 0.2 M KCl+0.2 M HCl (pH 2), (iii) 0.2 M CH_3COOH +0.2 M CH_3COONa (pH 4), (iv) 0.1 M CH_3COOH +0.1 M CH_3COONa (pH 6), (v) 0.01 M EDTA in 0.1 M HCl and (vi) 0.1 M thiourea (TU) in 0.01 M HCl.

TABLE 2—SEPARATIONS ACHIEVED ON TIN(IV)
DIETHANOLAMINE IMPREGNATED PAPERS

Time=3 h, Voltage applied=200 V

Sl. no.	Separations achieved*
1.	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.3)$
2.	$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}(0.0) - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}(+3.7)$
3.	$\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}(-0.5) - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.4)$
4.	$\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}(-0.9) - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.3)$
5.	$\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(+6.0) - \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}(-11.3)$
6.	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(+1.9)$
7.	$\text{Au}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.2)$
8.	$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}(0.0) - \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}(-1.1) - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.2)$
9.	$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}(0.0) - \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.3) - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}(+4.0)$
10.	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}(-1.0) - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}(+4.0)$
11.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}(-3.4) - \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(+6.3)$
12.	$\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(+5.8) - \text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}(-3.0) - \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}(-11.3)$
13.	$\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}(-11.4) - \text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}(-3.5) - \text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(+5.9)$
14.	$\text{Pd}^{\text{II}}(-11.4) - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(-1.8) - \text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(+6.4)$
15.	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(-1.7) - \text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}(-3.2)$
16.	$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(-3.0) - \text{Ag}^{\text{I}}(0.0) - \text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(+6.3)$
17.	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(+6.0) - \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}(-11.4)$
18.	$\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}(-0.5) - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}(+4.2)$
19.	$\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}(-0.8) - \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}(-2.7) - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}(+4.6)$
20.	$\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}(-2.7) - \text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}(-3.8) - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(-6.4)$
21.	$\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}(-2.8) - \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(-1.8) - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(-6.4)$
22.	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(-1.6) - \text{Co}^{\text{II}}(-2.7) - \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(-6.3)$
23.	$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}(0.0) - \text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(+11.4)$
24.	$\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}(-4.2) - \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}(0.0) - \text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}(+11.5)$
25.	$\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(+17.2) - \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(0.0) - \text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}(-3.5)$

*Background electrolyte: Sl. nos. 1–14; pH 1; Sl. nos. 15–17, pH 2; Sl. nos. 18–22, 0.01M EDTA in 0.1M HCl; Sl. nos. 23–25, 0.1M TU in 0.01M HCl.

Procedure: The electrode vessels were filled with equal volumes (150 ml) of background electrolyte solution. The centres of the strips were marked with pencil and the strips were soaked with the corresponding background electrolyte, the excess being removed by blotting. The strips were placed horizontally in the cassette. A drop of individual metal ion solution was placed in the middle of each strip separately. The cassette was then covered, and a potential of about 200 V was applied for 3 h. The migration of zones of ions was measured from the point of application to the middle of the zone. On the basis of the results observed in the case of individual metal ions, the experiment was repeated with synthetic binary or ternary mixtures of the particular metal ions of interest. For quantitative studies the spot area was cut into pieces and treated with 1 M of HNO_3 (20 ml) to elute the metal ion. The solution was evaporated to a small volume. Ag^{I} and Au^{III} were determined spectrophotometrically with dithiozone and stannous chloride respectively⁴.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.M.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

Experimental

Electrophoresis was carried out using a Laboratorium Felszerelések Gyara D 201 horizontal apparatus. A Perkin-Elmer 552 spectrophotometer was used for spectrophotometric measurement. All reagents were of AnalaR grade.

Chromatographic paper strips (40 × 2.5 cm) were first soaked with freshly prepared 0.1 M aqueous solution of stannic chloride, dried at room temperature and then passed through 0.4 M diethanolamine solution, and finally the impregnated strips were dried at room temperature.

Stock solutions of metal nitrate or chloride (0.1 M) were prepared in demineralised water. Platinum solution was prepared by dissolving chloroplatinic

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